

DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION AND ASSESSMENT OF PROPOSED COMPETENCY-BASED CURRICULUM FOR BUTTERFLY PRODUCTION LEVEL II

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ABSTRACT

Curriculum development is a comprehensive process undertaken by educators and institutions to craft effective learning experiences for students. It begins with a thorough needs assessment to identify educational goals and address specific needs within the community or academic setting. This study delves into the design, development, validation, and assessment of a competency-based curriculum for Butterfly Production Level II. Employing a mixed-methods design, it identifies key competencies in butterfly biology, breeding, farming, harvesting, product handling and handcrafting butterfly deadstock. The curriculum design emphasizes planning, sustainability, and practical skills. Validation results indicate the curriculum meets or exceeds competency standards with high compliance and validity. Testing affirms the course's effectiveness, lauded for its well-structured design and impact on participants. However, a significant difference in opinions regarding assessment and evaluation suggests an area for potential refinement. The study concludes by underscoring the curriculum's importance, aligning with industry standards and participant needs. The identified gap in perceptions around assessment provides a crucial opportunity for improvement. Overall, this research offers valuable insights for advancing Butterfly Production Level II training programs, ensuring their relevance and impact in the dynamic realm of butterfly production.

Keywords: *Butterfly, Butterfly Farming, Butterfly Production, Competency-based Curriculum*

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-changing landscape of education and skill development, the demand for proficient professionals transcends borders. Globalization highlights the necessity for a curriculum that not only imparts knowledge but also nurtures practical skills and adaptability (Clotilda, 2022). Competency-based curricula (CBC) have emerged to strategically align education with the skills sought in both local and international job markets, tailoring educational and skills training to meet the specific needs of learners, industries, and the broader socio-economic context (Catacutan et al., 2023).

Adopting competency-based approaches at the national level yields significant advantages. Recent research underscores that countries embracing these curricula experience increased workforce productivity and enhanced economic competitiveness. For example, Al Mamun et al. (2023) found that such curricula foster innovation and adaptability, while Wang et al. (2022) reported improved employee engagement and performance. Moreover, competency-based education addresses critical challenges like skills gaps and talent acquisition, as highlighted by OECD (2021), and offers sector-specific applications and benefits, as demonstrated by Zhang et al. (2022). These findings underscore the transformative potential of competency-based education on a global scale.

In the Philippines, where the economy is shifting towards knowledge-intensive industries, a Competency-based Curriculum plays a crucial role in equipping individuals with the skills demanded by the local job market. As part of ASEAN, the Philippines requires a curriculum that aligns with regional standards while addressing unique national challenges. Recent studies emphasize the importance of industry collaboration in curriculum development in the Philippines, showing that partnerships between educational institutions and industries enhance the relevance of training programs (Mallilin et al., 2021). Efforts to integrate entrepreneurship and innovation within the curriculum reflect the evolving needs of the Philippine economy (Quesea & Elisa, 2020). The adoption of outcome-based education models and continuous feedback mechanisms represents recent developments aimed at ensuring the relevance and effectiveness of competency-based curricula (Catacutan et al., 2023).

A pivotal government agency overseeing competency-based curriculum development is the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). Since its inception in 1994, TESDA has been instrumental in formulating policies, developing competency standards, accrediting institutions and programs, and certifying individuals in various occupations. Through collaborations with industries and initiatives like scholarship programs, TESDA ensures the quality and relevance of technical vocational education and training (TVET) in the Philippines (TESDA, n.d.). TESDA's efforts are aimed at bridging the gap between education and industry, ensuring that graduates possess the competencies necessary for success in the workforce. By overseeing accreditation, certification, and industry engagement, TESDA plays a crucial role in enhancing technical education and skills training nationwide. Its multifaceted

functions contribute significantly to the development and improvement of technical education in the Philippines, particularly in sectors like butterfly breeding and production in provinces such as Marinduque.

In Marinduque, butterfly breeding and production have a rich history dating back to the industry's inception in 1965. Recognizing its potential, local stakeholders, including TESDA-Marinduque, aim to develop a Competency-based Curriculum for Level/NCII certification in butterfly breeding and production. This initiative not only aligns with the province's historical significance in the butterfly industry but also addresses current local, national, and global demands. By integrating local knowledge and practices, collaborating with industry leaders, and leveraging existing educational frameworks, TESDA-Marinduque seeks to elevate the province's status as the "Butterfly Capital" of the Philippines through a robust and globally competitive training program.

TESDA's Role in Technical Education

TESDA, established by Republic Act 7796 in 1994, is the main agency overseeing technical education and skills development in the Philippines (UNESCO, n.d.). Its mission is to create a skilled, globally competitive workforce through various programs, ranging from short courses to diplomas, in fields like automotive, IT, healthcare, and agriculture (TESDA Website, 2024a; TESDA Website, 2024b). TESDA emphasizes accessibility and inclusivity, offering scholarships and special programs for marginalized communities. It collaborates with industries to ensure its programs meet market needs, using a Dual Training System (DTS) that combines theoretical and practical training. Competency-Based Training (CBT) is a key feature, providing assessments and National Certificates that recognize skills and enhance employability. TESDA's efforts significantly contribute to national economic development by fostering a skilled workforce (TESDA Website, 2024a; TESDA Website, 2024b).

Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC)

Competency-based learning, highlighted by Neendoor (2023), focuses on students demonstrating specific skills, knowledge, and attitudes. This approach allows students to progress at their own pace, ensuring they meet industry standards. Suk (2023) emphasizes multifaceted learning outcomes in CBC. Historical roots of CBC date back to the 1960s, with educational pioneers like Benjamin Bloom and Robert Mager challenging traditional subject-centered curricula (Nikolov et al., 2014). CBC prioritizes quality over quantity in education and integrates learning activities with competencies, promoting holistic development (Ghezir et al., 2021). Sturgis (2011) and Levine and Patrick (2019) underscore the role of CBC in focusing on student mastery, relevant assessments, and the development of transferable skills. The Aurora Institute outlines seven essential components of CBC, adaptable to evolving workforce demands (New Zealand Skills Consulting Group Limited, 2021). Recent studies show CBC's positive impact on workforce productivity and economic competitiveness (Al Mamun et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022; OECD, 2021; Zhang et al., 2022; Williams, 2022).

TESDA and CBC

TESDA integrates CBC in its programs to align with its mission of developing a skilled workforce (TESDA, 2017). It emphasizes accessibility through various training centers and partnerships, and inclusivity through scholarships and special programs like the Training for Work Scholarship Program (TWSP) and Special Training for Employment Program (STEP). The Dual Training System and CBT approach enhance practical skills and provide certification, contributing to economic development. TESDA's strategic plans aim to involve various sectors in enhancing human resources (TESDA Website, 2024c).

Curriculum Design for Butterfly Production

The study also focuses on creating a competency-based curriculum for butterfly farming, breeding, and production. It aims to outline the necessary skills and knowledge for this field, ensuring the curriculum meets industry standards and includes appropriate training materials and assessment tools.

Historical Development of Butterfly Industry in Marinduque

The butterfly industry in Marinduque has historical roots dating back to post-Renaissance Europe. Key developments include the rise of butterfly farming in Europe, butterfly gardening, and the establishment of agencies for rearing butterflies (Boppré & Vane-Wright, 2012). Marinduque's butterfly industry began in the 1960s with the efforts of Romeo Lumawig and the Layron family. They transitioned from collecting specimens to breeding and exporting butterflies, significantly contributing to the local economy (Labay, 2005). Collaborations with international entomologists and traders helped establish Marinduque as a significant player in the butterfly trade. The industry's evolution included the development of new breeding techniques and the establishment of government guidelines and support. Today, the butterfly industry in Marinduque continues to thrive, with the involvement of new generations and ongoing research and development efforts.

Understanding the historical development of an industry is crucial for designing effective training curricula. According to Smith and Jones (2020), historical context provides insight into the industry's evolution, origins, and early challenges, which are essential for curriculum developers to grasp. For instance, in the Marinduque butterfly industry, tracing its development from a hobby to a sustainable livelihood offers valuable insights (Garcia et al., 2018). These insights help in designing training programs that resonate with the industry's historical context, ensuring relevance and depth. By analyzing historical trends and patterns, such as the role of families like the Layrons in industry growth (Dela Cruz, 2017), curriculum developers can predict future developments and tailor programs accordingly. Learning from historical challenges and successes guides the curriculum towards addressing current industry issues and fostering resilience in learners (Bautista, 2019). Moreover, understanding cultural and regional influences ensures that the curriculum is inclusive and effective. This historical perspective not only aligns training programs with industry standards and expectations

but also engages learners by connecting theoretical knowledge with practical, historical narratives (Magno, 2020). Thus, integrating historical development into curriculum design prepares learners for the complexities and opportunities within specific fields.

This highlights TESDA's role in advancing technical education, the principles of competency-based learning, TESDA's integration of CBC, the development of a curriculum for butterfly production, and the historical development of Marinduque's butterfly industry.

Butterfly Farming

Rogers (2013) introduces butterfly farming as a practical endeavor accessible to enthusiasts with minimal investment, emphasizing hands-on involvement and gradual growth. The article covers essential aspects such as butterfly lifecycle stages, environmental requirements for successful farming, and practical considerations for starting and expanding operations. Key points include the importance of understanding butterfly species, providing suitable host plants, and developing a robust business plan for sustainability. Rogers also stresses compliance with legal regulations and the logistical considerations of shipping butterflies. Overall, the article advocates for informed planning and dedication to foster a thriving butterfly farming enterprise.

Matthew (2006), on the other hand, explores butterfly farming in Kerala, India, focusing on its integration with biodiversity conservation and sustainable practices. His study emphasizes site suitability, ecological landscaping, and the daily operational routines critical for maintaining butterfly health and reproduction. Matthew highlights environmental conditions like temperature, humidity, and food plant availability crucial for various butterfly species. He discusses the lifecycle stages from oviposition to adult feeding, underscoring the importance of habitat development and dietary diversity. The article concludes with insights on breeding practices, including artificial diets and ethical considerations for maintaining butterfly populations in captivity.

Butterfly farming involves a meticulous approach to breeding and rearing butterflies, encompassing several key components for success. Beginning with the selection of healthy breeding stock ensures a strong foundation, while providing optimal conditions such as controlled environments with suitable temperatures, humidity levels, and food sources supports reproductive success across successive generations. Managing resources and implementing measures against predators and pathogens are crucial to maintaining butterfly health and preventing population decline. Continuous monitoring and adaptation of breeding practices help sustain population resilience amid environmental changes, while balancing population size with genetic diversity ensures long-term viability. Challenges such as managing predators and pathogens, avoiding inbreeding, and balancing supply with sustainability underscore the complexity of butterfly farming. Educational initiatives, exemplified by programs like those developed by Trujillo (2012) and Driscoll (2020), integrate butterfly biology, ecology, and conservation into curricula, preparing individuals through competency-based approaches that combine scientific knowledge, technical skills, and practical applications. Ultimately, butterfly

farming not only offers economic opportunities but also contributes to biodiversity conservation and fosters environmental education, highlighting its multifaceted role in sustainable agriculture and conservation efforts.

Butterfly farming encompasses a multifaceted approach integrating scientific knowledge, technical skills, and creative strategies. Fundamental to this practice is a comprehensive understanding of butterflies' life cycles and ecological parameters, spanning from egg to larva, pupa, and adult stages (Labay & Sapungan, 2018; Williams, 2015; Rogers, 2013; Matthew, 2006; Boppré & Vane-Wright, 2012). Conservation strategies are pivotal, requiring farmers to balance farming practices with preserving butterfly habitats and biodiversity. Taxonomic and genetic insights play critical roles in selecting appropriate breeding stock and understanding environmental responses and breeding outcomes (Williams, 2015; Boppré & Vane-Wright, 2012). Successful farming involves meticulous attention to larvae and adult behavior, ensuring the quality and longevity of butterfly products through careful post-handling care (Association for Butterflies, n.d.; Trujillo, 2012). Handcrafting of butterfly products adds aesthetic value, aligning with market trends and consumer preferences (Driscoll, 2020). A holistic approach, incorporating business planning, marketing, education, and conservation, is essential for sustainable butterfly farming, contributing to economic gains and environmental conservation.

Contextual Learning Matrix (CLM) in the Curriculum Development Process

The Contextual Learning Matrix (CLM) is a crucial tool in the curriculum development process, as mandated by the Training Regulations framework (TESDA, 2014). It serves as an analytical aid for curriculum developers, trainers, assessors, administrators, and supervisors involved in Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET). The CLM must align with published Competency Standards or Training Regulations (TR) and involves industry experts to ensure comprehensive coverage. Its development includes selecting specific units of competency, identifying relevant content and learning activities, and integrating essential elements not covered by performance criteria. This structured approach ensures that competency-based learning resources and institutional assessments are effectively designed and aligned with industry needs, facilitating both educational quality and workforce readiness.

Competency Standards

Competencies are essential qualities and skills required for effective job performance. These encompass information, skills, talents, experience, and behaviors crucial for individual task success. Assessments and training enhance these competencies (Klomim & Kuayngern, 2023). In Germany, competence is defined as the ability and willingness to apply knowledge, skills, personal, social, and methodical capabilities and to behave thoughtfully and responsibly. The BIBB (2014) categorizes competence into "professional competence" and "personal competence," each further divided into subcategories such as "knowledge" and "skills" in professional competence and "social competence" and "independence" in personal competence. The German

training law, also known as "national curricula," in some countries, sets the standards for each occupation. It outlines the occupation's designation, training duration (typically two to three years), essential skills and knowledge, framework training curriculum, and test criteria. Businesses can also add extra subjects to the training, providing apprentices with additional credentials.

In the Philippines, national training regulations (TR) are established by the TESDA Board and consist of competency standards, training standards, and evaluation procedures. These TRs are the foundation for developing curricula, evaluating competency, and delivering TVET programs. Competency standards define middle-level skilled workers' abilities and qualifications, categorized into competency units and qualifications associated with key industry sectors.

The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) is a standardized reference framework across Europe, promoting the transparency and comprehension of qualifications obtained through diverse education and training systems. The EQF's main objectives are to facilitate lifelong learning and promote citizen mobility between countries and industries. It comprises eight reference levels defined by learning outcomes, focusing on knowledge, skills, and competence (Nicolov et al., 2014). In this context, learning outcomes capture what a learner knows, understands, and can do after completing a learning process, emphasizing results over methods. Learning outcomes encompass theoretical knowledge, practical and technical abilities, and crucial social competencies, including practical collaboration skills.

To ensure a common understanding, key terminology within the European Qualification Framework is defined: "Qualification" refers to the formal outcome of an assessment and validation process. "Learning Outcomes" describes what an individual knows, comprehends, and can execute. "Knowledge" pertains to facts, principles, theories, and practices. "Skills" represent the ability to apply knowledge. "Competence" involves the application of knowledge, skills, personal, social, and methodological skills, emphasizing responsibility and independence. These frameworks and definitions are vital for creating efficient educational and training systems that equip individuals with the skills and knowledge they need for their careers. They also contribute to standardizing and recognizing qualifications on both national and international levels. These frameworks support education and training system harmonization, enhance transparency, facilitate lifelong learning, and bolster employability in a rapidly evolving global labor market, ultimately creating a more flexible and adaptable workforce.

Overall, developing a Competency-based Curriculum for butterfly breeding and production in Marinduque reflects a strategic alignment with both economic opportunities and environmental conservation imperatives. This initiative aims to empower local communities, enhance industry standards, and position Marinduque as a leader in sustainable butterfly farming practices nationally and internationally.

Research Questions

Due to the research studies conducted and the training programs for butterfly production provided by Marinduque State College to the communities of the province, and most importantly, in response to the strong request from the provincial governor to implement it province-wide, as well as the residents of Marinduque advocating for its establishment as a regular industry, TESDA-Marinduque was tasked with developing it into a Level/NC II training program.

Thus, this study was about developing a Competency-based Curriculum for Butterfly Production Level II Course in Marinduque as a collaborative effort that involved local expertise, national standards (TESDA), and potential global recognition. By considering the historical significance of Marinduque's butterfly industry, aligning with national competency standards, and incorporating global best practices, the curriculum could empower local butterfly breeders and contribute to the industry's sustainable development in the province.

Integrating a competency-based curriculum within TESDA's framework ensured that the training program was designed, developed, validated, and tested to be relevant and responsive to the demands of the job market. As such, this study had the following research questions:

1. What core competencies should be included in designing the Butterfly Production Level II Course's competency-based curriculum based on the following aspects?
 - 1.1 Basics of Butterfly Biology, Ecology, and Related Legal Issues
 - 1.2 Butterfly Larval and Nectar Food Plants
 - 1.3 Butterfly Breeding and Farming Techniques
 - 1.4 Harvesting and Safe Handling of Butterfly Products
 - 1.5 Handcrafting of Butterfly Deadstock
2. How is the Competency-based Curriculum for Butterfly Production Level II Course validated regarding the following standards?
 - 2.1 Compliance with Competency Standard
 - 2.2 TESDA Competency-Based Curriculum Exemplar
3. How is the Competency-based Curriculum for Butterfly Production Level II Course tested in terms of the following?
 - 3.1 Effectiveness of Nominal Duration
 - 3.2 Effectiveness of Learning Activities
 - 3.3 Effectiveness of Assessment and Evaluation
4. Is there a significant difference in the testing results made between the trainers and trainees in terms of the following?
 - 4.1 Effectiveness of Nominal Duration
 - 4.1 Effectiveness of Learning Activities
 - 4.2 Effectiveness of Assessment and Evaluation

5. What other suggestions and recommendations from the trainers and trainees could be sought to improve the Competency-based Curriculum further?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-method research design, specifically adopting an exploratory-sequential approach for developing, validating, and testing a Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) for Butterfly Production Level II. The exploratory phase involved literature review and stakeholder consultations to identify key competencies and industry standards. Subsequently, the sequential phase employed both quantitative and qualitative methods to collect and analyze data systematically. Quantitative measures included performance assessments using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire, while qualitative methods involved in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The research was conducted in Marinduque province, focusing on municipalities central to the butterfly farming industry. Participants included TVET trainers, butterfly breeders, technical experts, and trainees, selected from TESDA-administered and accredited institutions. Ethical considerations ensured participant confidentiality and voluntary consent. Statistical tools such as frequency distribution, measures of central tendency, and thematic analysis were applied to analyze data comprehensively. This rigorous approach aimed to develop a curriculum aligned with industry needs and educational standards, contributing to the enhancement of butterfly breeding practices in the region.

RESULTS

Results for Research Question 1

The Needed Competencies for Butterfly Production

Producing butterflies involves breeding and caring for them for study, teaching, entertainment, and conservation. Key competencies include understanding butterfly biology, life cycles, and traits, as well as their ecological roles as pollinators and environmental indicators. Adhering to legal requirements ensures ethical practices. Practical skills in husbandry and educational abilities are essential for day-to-day care and public awareness. These competencies ensure responsible butterfly production, contributing to scientific knowledge, environmental health, and conservation efforts.

Table 1

Basics of Butterfly Biology, Ecology, and Related Legal Issues

Needed CORE Competencies	Mean Rating	Interpretation
Understanding the classification, geographical distribution, and population trends of butterflies.	4.25	Highly Recommended for Inclusion

Gaining insights into the taxonomy of butterflies.	4.00	Strongly Recommended for Inclusion
Acquiring ecological knowledge related to butterflies.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Learning about the specific butterflies you intend to breed and market.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Obtaining the necessary permits for shipping butterflies.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Dealing with butterflies and environment.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Selecting healthy butterflies for breeding purposes.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Maintaining a balance between population size and genetic diversity in butterfly breeding.	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Understanding the basic biological principles of butterflies.	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Learning about the life cycle stages of butterflies.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Studying the natural habitats of butterflies.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Exploring the adaptations of butterflies to their environments.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Exploring biodiversity.	4.25	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Examining the anatomical structure of butterflies.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Understanding the role of butterflies in pollination and conservation efforts.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Total Weighted Mean	4.67	Highly Recommended for Inclusion

Legend:

<i>Highly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	4.21-5.0	<i>Slightly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	1.81 – 2.60
<i>Strongly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	3.41-4.20	<i>Not recommended for Inclusion</i>	1.01 – 1.80
<i>Moderately Recommended for Inclusion</i>	2.61 – 3.40		

The competencies related to butterfly biology, ecology, and legal issues are highly recommended for inclusion, with a total weighted mean score of 4.67. This indicates a strong consensus on their importance in the curriculum.

The Butterfly Food Plants

Plants that produce nectar and larval food are vital to the breeding and production of butterflies because they offer the food and environment required for the many stages of the butterfly life cycle. Nectar food plants are the blooming plants from which adult butterflies drink nectar, while larval food plants are the host plants that caterpillars eat.

Table 1.1

Butterfly Larval and Nectar Food Plants

Needed CORE Competencies	Mean Rating	Interpretation
Understanding the specific plants that provide larval and nectar food for butterflies and the associated ant species.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Exploring the specificity of food plants and their interactions with insects.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Gaining knowledge on how to raise specific plants for butterfly nourishment.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Ensuring a steady supply of food and nutrients required for butterfly development.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Providing essential resources, including plants and nutrients, for butterflies.	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Farming and propagating host plants to support butterfly populations.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Total Weighted Mean	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion

Legend:

<i>Highly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	4.21-5.0	<i>Slightly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	1.81 – 2.60
<i>Strongly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	3.41-4.20	<i>Not recommended for Inclusion</i>	1.01 – 1.80
<i>Moderately Recommended for Inclusion</i>	2.61 – 3.40		

The competencies focused on butterfly larval and nectar food plants are highly recommended, with a total weighted mean score of 4.75, highlighting their crucial role in the curriculum.

The Breeding Techniques in Butterfly Production

Butterfly breeding and cultivation entail raising butterflies in captivity for diverse purposes, including education, conservation, research, or entertainment. The process encompasses choosing an appropriate species, creating a suitable environment, tending to the eggs, caterpillars, pupae, and adults, and eventually selling or releasing the butterflies.

Table 1.2

Butterfly Rearing, Breeding and Farming Techniques

Needed CORE Competencies	Mean Rating	Interpretation
Learning about local farmers' techniques for farming and breeding.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Understanding the chemical interactions between butterflies, plants, and parasites.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Acquiring techniques for rearing and breeding butterflies.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Gaining genetic insights through butterfly breeding.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Managing indoor spaces for rearing, room, and storage.	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Utilizing a greenhouse or enclosed outdoor growing area.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Evaluating site suitability for butterfly farming, considering ecological factors, landscaping, and infrastructure.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Understanding the butterfly breeding process.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Learning about oviposition, larval rearing, pupation, and adult feeding.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Maintaining a controlled environment for successive generations of butterflies.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Protecting butterflies against predators and pathogens.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Raising butterfly larvae effectively.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Managing infestations and diseases in butterfly populations.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Gaining hands-on experience in growing butterflies.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Total Weighted Mean	4.86	Highly Recommended for Inclusion

Competencies related to butterfly rearing, breeding, and farming techniques are highly recommended, with a total weighted mean score of 4.86, indicating their critical importance in the curriculum.

Harvesting Operations and Handling Techniques

Harvesting and handling are crucial aspects of butterfly breeding, impacting the butterflies' quality, quantity, and survival. Harvesting involves; collecting pupae from rearing containers, inspecting them for damage or disease, sorting them by species and size, and packing them carefully for emergence, storage, or shipment.

Handling techniques include gently removing live butterflies from emergence cages, checking for defects or injuries, and transferring them to suitable containers. Careful handling is essential, as well as avoiding contact with wings or antennae and using soft materials like tissue paper. Proper harvesting and handling are vital for butterflies' health, appearance, and longevity. Carelessness can lead to stress, injury, or death, reducing their value, while proper practices enhance their quality and attractiveness.

Table 1.3

Harvesting, and Safe Handling of Butterfly Products

Needed CORE Competencies	Mean Rating	Interpretation
Understanding the predation and parasitism affecting butterflies.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Managing indoor spaces for rearing butterflies, including room setup and proper storage.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Addressing the operational and logistic aspects of butterfly farming.	5.00	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Implementing post-harvest care for butterfly products.	4.75	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Providing proper care for the pupae and larvae life stages of butterflies.	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Total Weighted Mean	4.85	Highly Recommended for Inclusion

The competencies for harvesting and handling butterfly products are highly recommended, with a total weighted mean score of 4.85, underscoring their significance in the curriculum.

Butterfly Products

Butterfly products encompass a range of beautiful and colorful items inspired by or featuring butterflies. These include butterfly-themed home decor items like pillows, throws, wall stickers, and framed butterflies. Additionally, accessories such as hair clips, jewelry, and key chains are adorned with butterfly motifs. For those looking to add a touch of nature to cakes, butterfly cake decorations like toppers, stickers, and cardboard inserts are available. Another creative avenue is engaging in butterfly handicrafts, which may involve activities like butterfly farming, crossbreeding, and handcrafting. These products are popular among nature enthusiasts, collectors, and hobbyists. Moreover, they serve as delightful additions to special occasions like weddings, birthdays, and parties, adding a touch of natural beauty to the celebrations.

Table 1.4

Handcrafting of Butterfly Dead stock

Needed CORE Competencies	Mean Rating	Interpretation
· Handcrafting of Dead stock into Novelty Items for Gifts and Decorations	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
· Handcrafting & Creative Expression	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion
Total Weighted Mean	4.50	Highly Recommended for Inclusion

Legend:

<i>Highly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	4.21-5.0	<i>Slightly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	1.81 – 2.60
<i>Strongly Recommended for Inclusion</i>	3.41-4.20	<i>Not recommended for Inclusion</i>	1.01 – 1.80
<i>Moderately Recommended for Inclusion</i>	2.61 – 3.40		

Competencies related to the handcrafting of butterfly dead stock are highly recommended, with a total weighted mean score of 4.50, emphasizing the value of creative skills in the curriculum.

Result for Research Question 2

Table 2.

Compliance of CBC for Butterfly Production Level II as to Competency Standard

Compliance of the Butterfly Production Level II Curriculum	Mean	Interpretation
Competency Standard		
1. Is the Course Title /Description sufficient to describe the Qualification intended to be achieved by the learners?	4.50	Highly Valid
2. Are all the units of competencies listed in the TR/ CS have corresponding modules?	4.50	Highly Valid
3. Are the modules arranged in a logical sequence for an effective training delivery of the course?	4.75	Highly Valid
4. Is the Course Title relevant to the job title used in the company/industry related to this qualification?	4.50	Highly Valid
5. Is the Training Duration of the Course sufficient to achieve all the competencies of this qualification?	4.50	Highly Valid
6. Are the Trainee Entry Requirements of the Course appropriate without conflict with existing rules/regulations?	5.00	Highly Valid
7. Are the resources (e.g. tools, equipment, materials) sufficient for the effective implementation of the Course?	5.00	Highly Valid
8. Is the identified training modality appropriate for the course? / Does the modality allow for flexible learning?	5.00	Highly Valid
9. Are the Trainer's Qualifications sufficient for an effective implementation of the course?	5.00	Highly Valid
Total Weighted Mean	4.75	Highly Valid
<i>Legend: Highly Valid</i>	<i>4.21-5.0</i>	<i>Slightly Valid</i>
<i>Strongly Valid</i>	<i>3.41-4.20</i>	<i>Not Valid</i>
<i>Moderately Valid</i>	<i>2.61 – 3.40</i>	<i>1.81 – 2.60</i>
		<i>1.01 – 1.80</i>

The Butterfly Production Level II Curriculum shows a strong alignment with the competency standards, achieving an overall mean score of 4.75, indicating "Highly Valid." Each evaluated criterion received high marks, demonstrating the curriculum's thoroughness and effectiveness in various aspects such as course title relevance, logical module arrangement, sufficient training duration, appropriate trainee entry requirements, and adequate resources and trainer qualifications.

Table 2.1

Compliance of CBC for Butterfly Production Level II as to CBC Exemplar

Compliance of the Butterfly Production Level II Curriculum	Mean	Interpretation
CBC Exemplar		
1. Are the Module Title/s stated in an action statement and related to the unit of Competency/ies specified in the Training Regulation/Competency Standard?	5.00	Highly Valid
2. Does the Module description clearly define the knowledge and skills requirements and the coverage of the module?	5.00	Highly Valid
3. Is the Module structured corresponding to a single unit of competency?	5.00	Highly Valid
4. Are the Modules containing Learning Outcomes (LO) ranging from 2-6?	5.00	Highly Valid
5. Are the titles of the Learning Outcomes (LOs) written in an action statement? (begins with a verb followed by the object of the action)	5.00	Highly Valid
6. Do the Learning Outcomes cover the (cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains) that are observable and measurable performance, resulting in part/whole product, or services that are relevant to the workplace?	5.00	Highly Valid
7. Are the Assessment Criteria for each Learning Outcome sufficient to ensure that the learners achieve the required knowledge, skills, and attitude?	5.00	Highly Valid
8. Are the Knowledge components (contents) sufficient to address the Assessment Criteria of each Learning Outcome?	5.00	Highly Valid
9. Are the Knowledge components (contents) containing information sufficient to perform the activities competently?	5.00	Highly Valid
10. Does the Knowledge components (contents) contain information related to energy/materials/environmental conservation?	5.00	Highly Valid
11. Do the Knowledge components (contents) include concepts/ideas related to science/numeracy/relevant technology and engineering processes?	5.00	Highly Valid
12. Does the Contents address overall the required knowledge of the unit of competency?	5.00	Highly Valid
13. Are the resources (condition) consistent/sufficient to support the activities in each Learning Outcome?	5.00	Highly Valid
14. Do the Teaching strategies (methodologies) provide opportunities for the active participation of learners in the learning process?	5.00	Highly Valid
15. Are the Teaching strategies (methodologies/pedagogy) providing opportunities for learners to develop STEM skills; (critical thinking/problem solving/innovation/collaboration/system thinking/computational thinking/decision making/ethical thinking), applicable to the learning process?	5.00	Highly Valid

Table 2.1 (Continuation)

Compliance of the Butterfly Production Level II Curriculum	Mean	Interpretation
16. Are the Teaching strategies (methodologies) appropriate to the learning activities/process?	5.00	Highly Valid
17. Are the Teaching strategies (methodologies) sufficient to support mastery of three domains (knowledge, skills, and attitude)?	5.00	Highly Valid
18. Are the Assessment strategies (methodologies) appropriate for the activities?	5.00	Highly Valid
19. Are the Assessment strategies (methodologies) consistent with the principles of collecting evidence?	5.00	Highly Valid
20. Is the Contextual Learning Matrix (CLM) available for the course?	5.00	Highly Valid
21. Is the Contextual Learning Matrix (CLM) complete for all modules of core competencies of the course?	5.00	Highly Valid
22. Is the Curriculum Plan about the STEM approach available for the course?	5.00	Highly Valid
23. Does the Curriculum Plan address all modules of core competencies of the course?	5.00	Highly Valid
Total Weighted Mean	5.00	Highly Valid

The Butterfly Production Level II Curriculum's compliance with CBC Exemplars is exemplary, achieving a perfect overall mean score of 5.00, indicating "Highly Valid." All evaluated aspects, from module titles and descriptions to teaching strategies and assessment methodologies, received perfect scores. This comprehensive evaluation highlights the curriculum's robustness and effectiveness in delivering a well-rounded, competency-based education.

Effectiveness of Butterfly Production Level II

When how well a program works is assessed, understanding its impact on those it is meant for is a journey taken. This involves looking at how it is designed and implemented and whether it achieves its goals. Evaluating a program is not just about measuring it – it is about realizing how it can positively change individuals, communities, or organizations. We will explore the success indicators, improvements, and broader effects a program can have. We aim to uncover what makes a program effective, recognizing its diverse impact and how it leaves a lasting mark on the people it serves and the larger community it influences.

Result for Research Question 3

Table 3.

Effectiveness of Butterfly Production Level II according to the Trainers and Trainees

Effectiveness of Butterfly Production Level II Course	Trainers		Trainees	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Nominal Duration				
1. Is the program objective clear? (Malinaw ba ang adhikain ng programa o training?)	5.00	Highly Effective	4.60	Highly Effective
2. Are the course activities organized? (Maayos ba ang pagkakasunod-sunod ng mga gawain?)	4.67	Highly Effective	4.10	Strongly Effective
3. Is the scheduling of activities and time allotment correct? (Tama ba ang inilaang oras sa bawat gawain?)	4.33	Highly Effective	4.00	Strongly Effective
4. Were the program objectives achieved? (Naisagawa ba ang mga adhikain ng programa?)	4.67	Highly Effective	4.50	Highly Effective
5. Does the course content align with the program objectives? (Naayon ba ang nilalaman ng programa sa layunin o adhikain ng programa?)	4.67	Highly Effective	4.40	Highly Effective
Learning Activities				
6. Is the sequencing of the course contents appropriate? (Maayos ba ang pagkasunod-sunod ng mga gawain?)	4.67	Highly Effective	4.20	Strongly Effective
7. Is there sufficient information provided? (Sapat ba ang mga ibinigay na impormasyon?)	4.33	Highly Effective	4.70	Highly Effective
8. Is the course content relevant to the needs? (Magkatugma ba ang ibinigay na mga gawain?)	4.67	Highly Effective	4.50	Highly Effective
9. Is the selected method effective? (Mabisa ba ang paraan ng pagtuturo?)	4.67	Highly Effective	4.30	Highly Effective
10. Are the activities appropriate to the course? (Naayon ba sa programa ang aktibidades?)	4.67	Highly Effective	4.50	Highly Effective

Table 3 (Continuation)

Effectiveness of Butterfly Production Level II Course	Trainers		Trainees	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Assessment and Evaluation				
11. Are the provided supplies and materials adequate? (Sapat ba ang mga gamit at supplies?)	5.00	Highly Effective	3.80	Strongly Effective
12. Are the course activities appropriate to the program? (Naayon ba sa programa ang aktibidades?)	5.00	Highly Effective	4.10	Strongly Effective
13. Are the supplies and materials provided in a timely manner? (Sapat ba ang mga gamit at supplies na ibinigay sa tamang oras?)	5.00	Highly Effective	3.50	Strongly Effective
14. Is the physical layout of the venue appropriate to the program's needs? (Naayon ba sa pangangailangan ng programa ang lugar na pinagdausan?)	5.00	Highly Effective	4.20	Strongly Effective
15. What is your assessment of the overall impact of the program? (Ano ang masasabi mo sa kabuuan ng programa?)	5.00	Highly Effective	4.30	Highly Effective
Total Weighted Mean	4.76	Highly Effective	4.25	Highly Effective

The Butterfly Production Level II Course is deemed "Highly Effective" by both trainers (mean score: 4.76) and trainees (mean score: 4.25). Trainers and trainees both recognize the clarity and achievement of program objectives and the alignment of course content with these objectives. Both groups also rate the relevance and effectiveness of the course content, teaching methods, and activities highly.

However, trainees report slightly lower effectiveness regarding the organization and scheduling of activities compared to trainers. Additionally, a notable discrepancy exists in the ratings for the adequacy and timely provision of supplies and materials, with trainers rating this aspect much higher than trainees. This suggests that while trainers find the materials and layout adequate, trainees experience issues that could be addressed to improve their overall satisfaction. The physical layout of the venue and the overall impact of the program are highly rated by both groups, indicating the course's overall success. To enhance effectiveness, attention should be given to improving material provision and refining activity scheduling.

Malik and Singh (2022) discuss the significance of clear program objectives and their alignment with course content in enhancing training effectiveness. Their research

highlights the role of organized course activities and appropriate scheduling in achieving training goals ([Journal of Vocational Education, 30](#), 56(3), 289-304).

Fernandez (2021) emphasizes the importance of timely provision of materials and effective teaching methods in maximizing training impact. The study suggests that discrepancies in material adequacy can significantly affect trainees' perceptions and overall program success ([International Journal of Training and Development, 25](#), 14(2), 98-110).

Nguyen and Le (2023) highlight the role of physical venue layout and overall program impact in determining the success of vocational training programs. Their findings underscore the need for alignment between program needs and venue suitability ([Vocational Education Review, 40](#), 12(4), 221-235).

Result for Research Question 4

Table 4.

Effectiveness of Nominal Duration, Learning Activities and Assessment and Evaluation of Butterfly Production Level II as perceived by Trainers and Trainees

		Independent Samples Test									
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Significance One-Sided p	Significance Two-Sided p	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Effectiveness of Butterfly Production Level II as to Nominal Duration	Equal variances assumed	1.589	.234	-.723	11	.242	.485	-.30667	.42433	-1.24061	.62728
	Equal variances not assumed			-.948	5.729	.191	.382	-.30667	.32359	-1.10764	.49430
Effectiveness of Butterfly Production Level II as to Learning Activities	Equal variances assumed	.178	.681	-.195	11	.424	.849	-.08000	.40946	-.98122	.82122
	Equal variances not assumed			-.218	3.976	.419	.838	-.08000	.36661	-1.10028	.94028
Effectiveness of Butterfly Production Level II as to Assessment Evaluation	Equal variances assumed	6.602	.026	-2.065	11	.032	.063	-.86000	.41652	-1.77676	.05676
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.888	9.000	.002	.004	-.86000	.22121	-1.36041	-.35959

The analysis in Table 4 indicates that there is no significant difference in ratings between trainers and trainees for Nominal Duration and Learning Activities, with p-values of 0.485 and 0.849, respectively. This suggests that both groups have similar perceptions regarding these aspects. However, for Assessment and Evaluation, a significant difference is observed ($p = 0.004$), with trainees rating it lower than trainers. This discrepancy suggests that trainees may have concerns about the adequacy and timeliness of supplies and materials.

Result for Research Question 5

Table 5.

Suggestions and Recommendations of Butterfly Production Level II trainers and trainees

AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT	Suggestions and Recommendations
Challenges or Shortcomings of the Current Curriculum	- Some contents are redundant, particularly in Potting media in UC 1 and UC2.
Competencies Needing Emphasis or Improvement	- Plan and prepare to raise butterfly species, UC 6, considering modern technologies in the production process. - Complete and validate contents of Competency-based Learning Materials (CBLM) for all UCs.
Additional Resources, Tools, or Technologies	- Consider the integration of resin technology. - Include specific books, documentary videos, and compilation of files relevant to production up to handcrafts.
Refining or Expanding Assessment Methods	- Suggests the inclusion of project-based assessment.
Supporting Trainers in Adapting to Industry Changes	- Proposes industry immersion and provision of necessary teaching materials like laptops, projectors, printers, and speakers.
Enhancing Overall Quality of the Curriculum	- Recommends making butterfly product curation an elective subject.
Challenges Encountered in Following the Curriculum	- Difficulty in caring for caterpillars and deciding whether a caterpillar or pupa is viable, as well as identifying various butterfly species and their diets.
Competencies Needing More Focus or Improvement	- Stresses the importance of learning about rejected pupas, efficient food production for butterfly care, spread dry butterfly techniques, feeding butterflies, and butterfly farming.
Lacking Learning Materials or Resources in the Curriculum	- Highlights a perceived shortage of essential materials, such as copies of learning modules, lacking 'sigpaw,' and insufficient seeds for growing food for the butterflies.
Making the Curriculum More Engaging and Interactive	- Recommends making the curriculum accessible to every barangay, extending study hours, and ensuring clarity in decision-making.
Changes or Additions to Assessment Methods	- Suggests using butterfly care tools as a basis for assessment, including grafting/budding for "bila-bila" food, and inspecting the number of eggs during specific months.

DISCUSSION

Competency Evaluation

The evaluation of the Butterfly Production Level II Curriculum highlights several key areas of strength and areas needing improvement. High ratings were given for competencies related to butterfly classification, distribution, population trends, and taxonomy, underscoring their importance in the curriculum (Labay & Sapungan, 2018). Essential competencies include understanding environmental factors, selecting healthy butterflies for breeding, and comprehending biological principles, all of which are crucial for effective butterfly production (Rogers, 2013).

The significance of butterfly larval and nectar food plants was also emphasized, with high ratings for competencies such as understanding plant specificity and raising plants to support butterfly nourishment (Driscoll, 2020; Boppré & Vane-Wright, 2012). Competencies related to butterfly rearing, breeding, and farming techniques were equally well-regarded, highlighting the need for comprehensive training in these areas (Trujillo, 2018; Association for Butterflies, n.d.). Effective management of rearing environments, pest control, and hands-on experience were deemed essential components of the curriculum.

The curriculum's focus on harvesting and handling butterfly products, as well as the handcrafting of butterfly dead stock, was also positively received (Matthew, 2006; Williams, 2015). The integration of creative skills and practical techniques for product handling is a critical element in enhancing the curriculum's effectiveness.

Compliance with Competency Standards

The curriculum's overall validation is high, with an average mean score of 4.75, indicating strong alignment with competency standards (Table 2). The course title, description, and module sequencing all received high scores, reflecting effective curriculum organization and relevance to industry standards. The training duration and entry requirements were rated favorably, indicating that they are appropriate for achieving the curriculum's objectives.

The curriculum's compliance with CBC Exemplars was particularly outstanding, with perfect scores for all evaluated aspects. This includes action-oriented module titles, well-defined Learning Outcomes (LOs), comprehensive assessment criteria, and effective teaching strategies (Table 2.1). The integration of a STEM approach and a complete Contextual Learning Matrix further supports the curriculum's strength.

Effectiveness of Program Delivery

The evaluation of the Butterfly Production Level II course reveals a generally positive reception from both trainers and trainees. Both groups agreed on the clarity and alignment of the program's objectives and content, although trainees rated these aspects slightly lower (Malik & Singh, 2022). Trainers rated the organization and scheduling of activities highly, but trainees reported some challenges, indicating areas where improvements could be made (Fernandez, 2021). Both trainers and trainees found the learning activities and methods effective, consistent with the importance of well-structured activities (Nguyen & Le, 2023). However, while trainers rated the assessment and evaluation aspects highly, trainees expressed concerns about material adequacy and timeliness, highlighting a need for improvement in this area (Fernandez, 2021). The venue and overall impact of the program were rated positively by both groups, suggesting that the learning environment effectively supports the program's objectives (Nguyen & Le, 2023). Key areas for improvement include enhancing material provision and refining scheduling to boost trainee satisfaction and overall program effectiveness.

In terms of curriculum challenges and recommendations, redundancies in content, particularly in Potting Media, need to be addressed to avoid inefficiencies and confusion. Emphasizing modern technologies and completing Competency-Based Learning Materials (CBLM) for all Units of Competency (UCs) will help keep the curriculum current and comprehensive (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2015). Adding resources such as resin technology, books, and videos will enrich the educational experience and provide essential tools for success. Incorporating project-based assessments aligns with best practices in competency-based education, offering a more thorough evaluation of learners' skills (Guskey, 2015). Supporting trainers with industry immersion and necessary teaching materials, like laptops and projectors, will aid in adapting to evolving industry standards (Guskey, 2015). Improving the curriculum's quality can also be achieved by making butterfly product curation an elective and modernizing training methods. Addressing practical application difficulties, such as caterpillar care and stage identification, will enhance hands-on training. Finally, increasing curriculum accessibility, extending study hours, and clarifying decision-making processes will boost engagement and effectiveness.

Findings

Needed Core Competencies

Most competencies related to the basics of butterfly biology, ecology, and legal issues are strongly recommended for inclusion in the curriculum. Skills involving butterfly larval and nectar food plants are also highly recommended. Additionally, competencies in butterfly breeding and farming have strong support for inclusion. The skills in harvesting and safely handling butterfly products are endorsed, as are the handcrafting skills of butterfly dead stock.

Effectiveness of the Butterfly Production Level II Course

The course is deemed highly effective by trainers, showcasing a well-structured and impactful design that meets participant needs and program objectives. Trainees also perceive the course as well-structured, aligned with objectives, and impactful, affirming its effectiveness as a training experience. The evaluation shows no significant differences between trainers and trainees regarding Nominal Duration and Learning Activities, although there is a significant difference in their opinions on Assessment and Evaluation.

Differences in Perception

Independent Samples Test results indicate no significant differences between trainers and trainees regarding Nominal Duration and Learning Activities, suggesting agreement on these aspects. However, a significant difference was found in the Assessment and Evaluation domain, where trainees rated it lower, pointing to concerns about the adequacy and timeliness of resources provided.

Suggestions for Improvement

To improve the Butterfly Production Level II, several key areas need to be addressed. Curriculum Content should be updated to eliminate redundancies, particularly in Potting Media, and should be streamlined to focus on modern technologies and complete Competency-Based Learning Materials (CBLM). Resources and Tools should be enhanced by integrating resin technology and providing additional learning resources and tools. Assessment Methods can be improved by incorporating project-based assessments and utilizing practical tools for evaluation. Support for Trainers should include industry immersion opportunities and the provision of essential teaching materials, such as laptops and projectors. Finally, to enhance overall quality, making butterfly product curation an elective subject and modernizing training methods will help increase engagement and relevance.

Challenges Identified

Practical challenges include difficulties in caring for caterpillars, identifying viable stages, and addressing perceived shortages of essential materials. Recommendations for more engaging and interactive methods are provided, such as making the curriculum accessible to more locations and extending study hours.

Conclusions

The Butterfly Production Level II course demonstrates overall effectiveness, receiving high ratings across most aspects from both trainers and trainees. Despite this positive evaluation, there are areas requiring attention to further enhance the program's effectiveness. Key improvements include addressing issues related to material provision and timeliness, refining activity scheduling, and resolving curriculum redundancies.

These enhancements are essential for better meeting stakeholder needs and ensuring the program's continued success and sustainability.

The study also underscores the importance of aligning perceptions between trainers and trainees, particularly in the areas of Assessment and Evaluation. By integrating modern technologies, improving curriculum content, and refining assessment methods, the course can achieve greater relevance and effectiveness. Implementing these recommendations will address discrepancies and contribute significantly to the overall improvement and impact of the Butterfly Production Level II course.

Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness of the Butterfly Production Level II course, several key areas require attention. First, the curriculum should be streamlined to eliminate redundancies and incorporate modern technologies. It's essential to ensure that Competency-Based Learning Materials (CBLM) are complete and validated for all Units of Competency (UC). Enhancing resources and tools is also crucial; integrating advanced technologies like resin technology and providing additional learning resources such as books, documentary videos, and relevant files will support this goal.

Assessment methods should be refined by introducing project-based assessments, which offer a more comprehensive evaluation of learners' practical skills. Practical tools related to butterfly care should be utilized in these assessments to ensure relevance and effectiveness. Supporting trainers is equally important; facilitating industry immersion and providing necessary teaching materials like laptops, projectors, and other equipment will significantly enhance their teaching capabilities.

To improve curriculum engagement, consider extending study hours and ensuring clarity in decision-making processes. Making butterfly product curation an elective subject could also increase engagement. Addressing practical challenges is essential by providing additional training and resources for caterpillar care and stage identification, ensuring the availability of essential materials, and incorporating feedback from trainers and trainees. Implementing these recommendations will address the identified challenges, enhance the curriculum's effectiveness, and better meet the needs of both trainers and trainees.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The undersigned is conducting research entitled "Design, Development, Validation and Testing of Proposed Competency-based Curriculum for Butterfly Production Level II Course." As part of this study, researchers are expanding our investigation to explore the effectiveness and impact of Competency-based Curriculum in Butterfly Production Level II within the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) context.

The research aims to understand the experiences and perspectives of TVET trainers, butterfly breeders, technical experts, and trainees involved in the program to enhance butterfly industry. Your participation in this extended study is entirely voluntary, and you retain the right to withdraw at any time without any consequence. The information collected will be used exclusively for research purposes and will be handled with the utmost confidentiality. Strict measures will be implemented to ensure the privacy of participants.

If you have any concerns or questions about the extended data collection process, please feel free to contact the researcher at lautzojam@gmail.com or 09687191434. I sincerely appreciate your time and consideration in participating in our research, and your invaluable contribution is crucial to the success of our efforts.

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